

BiPhenom

Multifunctional Biophenols for Safe and Recyclable Materials

Call topic: **HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-02**

Grant Agreement n° **101135107**

D2.1: Policy brief on biomass sidestreams for value-added products

Authors: Marc Borrega, Petri Widsten, Melissa Agustin, Taina Ohra-aho, Elmeri Pienihäkkinen

Affiliation: VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd.

Deliverable nature	Policy Brief
Dissemination level	PU
Contractual delivery date	31.3.2025 (M10)
First delivery	31.3.2025
Current version delivery	9.3.2026
Version	2.0

Biophenols from biomass sidestreams for value-added products

Context

The EU's updated Bioeconomy Strategy (2025)¹ emphasizes the sustainable supply and use of biomass to reduce dependence on fossil-based chemicals, decrease pollution, and support circular material flows. Each year, the EU generates around 1 billion tons of primary biomass², with large quantities of sidestreams originating from forestry, agriculture, and food industries. These sidestreams are often underutilized yet represent a major potential source of bio-based chemicals such as biophenols (e.g., lignin and tannins) that can replace many harmful petrochemicals used today.

This policy brief summarizes the availability, biophenol content, logistics, and current use of ten selected biomass sidestreams. It identifies key barriers and opportunities for enabling their valorisation as biophenol sources for development of safe, sustainable, and recyclable materials.

Key recommendations

- 1** Promote high-value utilization of biomass sidestreams to accelerate the deployment of bioeconomy strategies by reducing reliance on incineration for energy and integrating impacts of biogenic CO₂ emission into policy instruments.
- 2** Support the development of flexible, scalable extraction technologies for biophenols capable of processing diverse sidestream types to improve yields and enable industrial uptake, thus strengthening EU competitiveness in sustainable bio-based solutions.
- 3** Improve logistics and regional infrastructure to support sidestream collection and supply by prioritizing streams that are available year-round, centralized at industrial sites, and ready for transport without extensive pre-processing.

¹ A Strategic Framework for a Competitive and Sustainable EU Bioeconomy. COM/2025/960 final, 27.11.2025.

² Biomass supply and uses in the EU. Publications Office of the European Union, DOI:10.2760/368529.

Scoping of biomass sidestreams as biophenol sources

Ten sidestreams from forestry, agriculture, and food industries are selected for evaluation: tree bark, wood sawdust, logging residues, cereal straw, fruit tree pruning residues, horticultural residues, olive stones, grape stalks, brewer's spent grain (BSG), and nut shells. Biomass sidestreams with negligible biophenol content (e.g., from fisheries, municipal waste) are excluded from the analysis.

Availability of sidestreams in the EU-27

The selected sidestreams combined are generated in quantities exceeding 350 million tons annually³ (Fig. 1). Cereal straw is the most abundant sidestream, followed by logging residues and fruit tree prunings. However, sustainable availability is typically 50–65% of total biomass because a fraction must remain onsite to prevent soil erosion and depletion of nutrients. The amounts of cereal straw here reported are conservative as they exclude other cereals than wheat, maize, barley, and oat. Two-thirds of the logging residues originate from coniferous tree species (spruce, pine), and the rest from deciduous species. Fruit tree prunings are mainly from olive orchards and grapevines, which account for more than half of the total quantities.

Figure 1. Potential availability in the EU-27 of selected sidestreams from forestry, agriculture, and food processing industries. Amounts in million tons per year.

Biophenol content

Lignin is one of the main structural components and a dominant biophenol in lignocellulosic biomass, while tannins and other minor phenolics are significant in some streams such as bark from conifers and grape stalks. Accordingly, the highest biophenol contents (35–40% of dry mass) are found in tree bark and grape stalks. Other sidestreams with high biophenol content (>30%) are nut shells and olive stones. Cereal straw and horticultural residues have the lowest biophenol contents (<20%) due to low lignification of the plant's stems.

Logistics

The utilization of biomass sidestreams as sources of biophenols (or other chemical components) may require that the sidestreams are collected and transported to industrial facilities for processing. Therefore, logistics strongly influence the feasibility of sidestream valorisation. Tree bark and wood sawdust offer the best logistical performance as they are available year-round, are located at industrial facilities, and require no pre-processing. Other sidestreams located at industrial sites (olive stones, nut shells, grape stalks, BSG) present moderate logistical complexity but seasonal variation remains a barrier. Finally, fruit tree prunings are the most challenging stream from a logistics perspective, as they are scattered over large areas, are seasonal, and require chipping or compacting before transport.

³ FAOSTAT database, year 2022: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data>

Current use of sidestreams

Waste or low-value sidestreams hold higher valorisation potential than sidestreams already used in high-value applications. Based on current practices, the main sidestream uses can be grouped into 5 categories: disposal (i.e., waste), energy production, soil improvement, animal feed, and material formulation (Fig. 2). Fruit tree prunings, horticultural residues, grape stalks, and BSG are low value or even waste streams, often landfilled or incinerated without energy recovery. Tree bark, sawdust, forest residues, olive stones, and nut shells are frequently used as industrial fuel. Many of the sidestreams are also used for soil improvement, for instance logging or harvesting residues are partly left on the field to protect soil quality, and bark is used as mulch in gardening or landscaping. Cereal straw and BSG find use as animal feed, either as source of fibre (straw) or protein (BSG). Wood sawdust is the only sidestream widely used in higher-value processes for material applications, such as pulping or manufacturing of composite panels.

Figure 2. Main current uses of selected sidestreams, from lower (bottom) to higher (top) value.

Conclusions

Biomass sidestreams containing significant amounts (>25%) of biophenols are available at scale in the EU, representing a major potential resource for circular bioeconomy development. Regional differences exist, with forestry residues dominating northern Europe and agricultural residues dominating southern regions, indicating a need for tailored regional biorefinery models. Logistics are decisive, as streams that are centralized, available year-round, and pre-processing-free offer the best opportunities. Sidestream incineration remains a widespread practice and undermines circularity and increases biogenic CO₂ emissions. Policy interventions, technology development, and improved logistics are essential to unlocking their value. By prioritizing high-value applications and reducing reliance on incineration, the EU can strengthen its bioeconomy, support climate targets, and enhance resource efficiency.

Selected sources of information

- Alakangas E, Hurskainen M, Laatikainen-Luntama J, Korhonen J. 2016. Properties of indigenous fuels in Finland. VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland. VTT Technology No. 272 <https://publications.vtt.fi/pdf/technology/2016/T272.pdf>
- Aliaño-González MJ, Gabaston J, Ortiz-Somovilla V, Cantos-Villar E. 2022. Wood Waste from Fruit Trees: Biomolecules and Their Applications in Agri-Food Industry. *Biomolecules*, 12(2), 238. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom12020238>
- Biomass production, supply, uses and flows in the European Union – First results from an integrated assessment, Publications Office, 2018. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/539520>
- Buffington J. 2014. The economic potential of brewer's spent grain (BSG) as a biomass feedstock. *Advances in Chemical Engineering and Science* 4, 308-318. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/aces.2014.43034>

- EU biomass supply, uses, governance and regenerative actions – 10-year anniversary edition, Publications Office of the European Union, 2025. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/6511190>
- García-Martín JF, Cuevas M, Feng CH, Álvarez-Mateos P, Torres-García M, Sánchez S. 2020. Energetic valorisation of olive biomass: olive tree pruning, olive stones and pomaces. *Processes* 8(5), 511. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr8050511>
- Løvdal T, Van Droogenbroeck B, Eroglu EC, Kaniszewski S, Agati G, Verheul M, Skipnes D. 2019. Valorization of tomato surplus and waste fractions: a case study using Norway, Belgium, Poland, and Turkey as examples. *Foods* 8(7), 229. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods8070229>
- Muilu-Mäkelä R, Brännström H, Weckroth M, Kohl J, et al. 2024. Valuable biochemicals of the future: The outlook for bio-based value-added chemicals and their growing markets. *Natural resources and bioeconomy studies*. Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke), 86 p. <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-380-976-5>
- Searle S, Malins C. 2013. Availability of cellulosic residues and wastes in the EU. The International Council on Clean Transportation (ICCT), White Paper, 29 p. https://theicct.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/ICCT_EUcellulosic-waste-residues_20131022.pdf (accessed 18th March 2025)
- Thorenz A, Wietschel L, Stindt D, Tuma A. 2018. Assessment of agroforestry residue potentials for the bioeconomy in the European Union. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 176, 348-359. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.12.143>
- Valle C, Grillo G, Calcio Gaudino E, Ponsetto P, Mazzoli R, Bonavita G, Vitale P, Pessione E, Garcia-Moruno E, Costantini A, Cravotto G, Tabasso S. 2025. Grape stalks valorization towards circular economy: a cascade biorefinery strategy. *ChemSusChem* e202402536, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.202402536>

The BioPhenom project, funded under the call HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-02, is a research and innovation action carried out by 12 European partners from 10 countries. The main target of the project is to explore the isolation and utilization of biophenols from selected biomass sidestreams for replacement of substances of very high concern (SVHC) in the development of safe, sustainable, and recyclable materials. All the steps along the value chains are guided by the Safe and Sustainable by Design framework recommended by the European Commission.

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement No: 101135107

Innovate
UK

This work was supported by UKRI
Horizon Europe Underwriting –
Innovate UK Council [1005409].

Project funded by

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This work has received funding from
the Swiss State Secretariat for
Education, Research and Innovation
(SERI).
Grant Agreement No: 24.00212

For more information, please contact:

Marc Borrega, VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd., marc.borrega@vtt.fi